

Table Alternative Proteins: Supporting Document

-Feedback from FEASTS to DG RDT-

Contributions for an EU policy on Alternative Proteins

PROJECT

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1. Scope:

This document supports the filling of a “250707 Table Alternative proteins”, which is part of an interaction between the different projects of Horizon4Protein and Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (DG RTD), which kick off meeting took place in November 2024. The presentation provided by FEASTS on such meeting can be found on [Link](#)

Follow-up activities included the evaluation of the Food 2030 R&I framework, which report has been complete and published in under the topic “Shaping the future of food research and innovation – Insights and recommendations from Food 2030 experts”, by EU DG RTD and Duncan, J., Publications Office of the European Union, 2025, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/8711448>. Note that this report does not mention Cultivated Meat (CM) and Cultivated Seafood (CSF), nor FEASTS project; as clarified, it was decided not to include projects that were in the first phase.

The filling of the **250707 Table Alternative proteins** is an initiative from DG RDT, which scope was stated to

- “gather specific information on the sources of proteins used in Horizon4Protein projects, on the **specific food analysed**, on the **production processing**”;
- provide “**recommendations** which can have an impact on the current EU regulatory framework”,
- “collecting this data in order to increase the scientific knowledge on the projects targeting alternative proteins” and to
- “understand the potential of alternative proteins to access to the market.”

To improve the readability of the contents filled on the table and provide additional background, we have prepared this accompanying document.

Currently FEASTS has reached its mid-term and as work progresses a more substantial body of knowledge and outputs are becoming available, which can support decision making processes and further policies. Importantly, on the scope of EU Food Diversification strategies it is important to include knowledge and information on CM/CSF. As such, while this document provides some initial insights, FEASTS consortiums is available and keen to further interact with DG RTD and provide further structured feedback on specific topics.

2. Layout

Meat products derived from cell lines can play a pivotal role in achieving the EU
This document follows the table entries supplied by D RD-RDT, which for the case
of CM and CSF products can be organized as:

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1. General info on the project

- HORIZON Project
- Coordinators
- Timeline
- Proteins sources

2. Specific information on protein sources

- Species/Strain
- Food sources
- Proteins produced

3. General information on the sector

- Processing
- Recommendations
- Comments

3. Supporting Information on “Table Alternative Proteins” content.

3.1. General info on the project

3.1.1 HORIZON Project: FEASTS

FEASTS: Project title: Fostering European Cellular Agriculture for Sustainable Transition Solutions (Project no. 101136749) was granted under the call Call: HORIZON-CL6-2023-FARM2FORK-01

More info on:

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101136749>

<https://feasts-innovation.eu/>

3.1.2 Coordinators: IST-ID

FEASTS consortium is comprised by 35 organisations from 15 European countries and 2 non-European countries

3.1.3 Timeline: Dec 2023 -Nov 2026

Currently at month 21 (out of 36)

3.1.4 Proteins sources: Animal cells

FEASTS is focused on the CM and CSF. Therefore, the protein source ais obtained from cultivated animal cells (intracellular and extracellular). Such cells can be primary cells or cell lines, and they are proliferated to obtain an animal cell biomass which is them used for non-structured or structured food products, which can or not be hybrid products (i.e. include also plant/fungi/other vegan ingredient sources).

3.2 Specific information on protein sources

3.2.1. Species/Strain

While the initial suggestion for table entries was “cell-lines from porcine, ovine and avian species” and “Several fish cell-lines”, we believe we service better this requested by categorizing the cell sources from (i) terrestrial and avian species according with Eurostart meat categories ([Link](#)) and for (ii) seafood according with FAO/ISSCAAP nomenclature ([General link](#), [Specific link](#)). These allows to assess the state of animal cellular food products, as intended, from protein source perspective. Therefore, the entry categories on the table are protein from cellular produced food from:

- Veal and Beef: Bovine: *Bos taurus*, *Bubalus bubalis*
- Pigmeat (Porcine): *Sus scrofa*
- Ovine (Lamb, Mutton) and Caprine: *Ovis aries*, *Capra Hircus*
- Poultry meat (Avian: chicken, turkey, duck): *Gallus gallus*, *Meleagris gallopavo*, *Anas platyrhynchos domesticus*
- Freshwater fish (carp, trout, perch)
- Diadromous fish (salmon, trout, sturgeon)
- Marine fish (tuna, seabream, meagre, seabass, mackerel) and other marine species (Crustaceans, Molluscs)

3.2.2 Food sources

- **Cultivated Veal and Beef Meat:** Animal protein from bovine origin, mainly muscle cells which can be presented as unstructured food (e.g. hamburgers, meatballs) or structure food (e.g. steaks). These products can be prepared as hybrid products (e.g. 20% to 70% bovine cells, and 80% to 30% plant/fungi/microbial-based components). Current companies in the EU include Mosa Meat (primary cells and others) and Meatable (pluripotent cells), or UK (Ivy Farm Technologies), while companies in Israel (Aleph Farms) have high TRLs. FEASTS is studying the development of culture media for bovine cells, as well as strategies to develop 3D printed product prototypes using bovine cell biomass. FEASTS is also designing and modelling bioprocesses and performing a Technical-Economical Analysis and Life Cycle Assessment for bovine cell biomass production.

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- **Cultivated Pig Meat:** Animal protein from pPorcine origin, both muscle and fat, with fat development currently at higher TRLs, which can be presented as unstructured or structured food, as well as hybrid products (e.g. bacon made of plant-based ingredients and cell-based fat to improve consumer experience). Current companies in the EU include Meatable, Mewery, Cultimate (FEASTS' partner) Cubiq, in the UK (Hoxtom Farms, Ivy Farm) and in the US Clever Carnivore and Mission Barns (already deployed on the US market). FEASTS, through BrunoCell is deploying an open-access cell line for porcine cell.
- **Cultivated Ovine Meat:** Animal protein from ovine muscle, can be presented as unstructured or structured food, as well as hybrid products (bacon made of plant-based ingredients and cell-based fat to improve consumer experience). With cell line development in the UK by PluriCells, Roslin Tech, Uncommon and by FEASTS, through BrunoCell, which is developing an ovine cell line.
- **Cultivated Poultry Meat:** Animal protein from avian origin, both muscle, fat and others. Avian cell-based foods currently have the highest TRLs, both for human (regulatory submissions, approvals or products deployed in the US, UK, Singapore, Israel and EU) and pet food (UK). Can be presented as unstructured or structured foods, as well as hybrid products (with animal cell content ranging from 20 to 70% and plant/fungi/microbial-based ingredients from 80 to 30%). Current companies in EU include Gourmey (Foie gras, FEASTS partner) and Vital Meat (chicken cells, FEASTS partner), companies in US (Upside Foods, Good Meat – chicken, regulatory clearance and approved to sell), Australia (Vow, quail), Israel (Believer Meats – regulatory clearance in the US) and the UK (Meatly – pPet food, regulatory clearance). FEASTS, through BrunoCell is developing avian cell lines.
- **Cultivated Freshwater Seafood:** Animal protein from freshwater fish, mainly muscle. Can be presented as unstructured or structured food, as well as hybrid products. Current companies in the EU include BLUU Seafood.
- **Cultivated Diadromous Fish Meat:** Animal protein from diadromous fish origin, mainly muscle. Can be presented as unstructured or structure food, as well as hybrid products. Current companies in EU focused on salmon include BLUU, and on US WildType (regulatory clearance and approved to sell).

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- **Cultivated Marine Seafood:** Animal protein from fish and marine animals of saltwater origin, mainly from muscle tissue. Can be presented as unstructured or structured food, as well as hybrid products. Current companies in EU include BLUU Seafood and Fishaway (FEASTS external stakeholder pursuing several marine fish species), as well as Cell4Food (Octopus); in the US include BlueNalu (several) and Atlantic Fish (several); in Israel Wanda fish, and in Singapore, Umami Bioworks (grouper, eel and tuna, FEASTS external stakeholder). At FEASTS, partners are developing fish cell lines and structured 3D-bioprinted seafood prototypes of fish foods.

3.2.3. Proteins produced

The proteins remain as part of the cellular and extracellular matrix and are not individually processed. They are produced naturally by muscle and connective tissue cells during cell culture. They include full panel of the regular proteins present on the animal meat, such as myosin heavy chain, troponin, tropomyosin, titin, alpha actin, actin, collagen, fibronectin. FEASTS will tackle nutritional assessment and safety on D3.5, D5.2 and D5.4.

3.3 General information on the sector

3.3.1. Processing

1. The product

Cultivated Meat (CM) and Cultivated Seafood (CSF) are produced by cultivating cells on bioreactor and using such cells to prepare final products. The final products are unstructured or structured products, which can be hybrid or not.

2. The general process

There is not a universal process for CM and CSF, instead each technology developer put forward different processes looking for process efficiency and product quality according with target features of the final product envisaged (nutritional, sensorial, etc), and specific process goals (food security, environmental performance, affordability). To provide an overview of the several possible processes trajectories and products please see FEASTS Milestone 8 ([Link](#)) or online tool ([Link](#))

The processes includes (i) cell cultivation steps, i.e cell isolation, cells proliferation (expansion), and in some cases, inducing cells differentiation/maturation to produce muscle-specific proteins; (ii) Cell biomass harvesting, including downstream and storage processing steps (centrifugation, washing, and mechanical structuring, and packaging); (iii) Food formulation steps (mixing with other components), to obtain final food products, which can be unstructured or structured products, for example using scaffolding or 3D printing. The products can be or not hybrid products (e.g. 20% to 70% cells, and 80% to 30% plant/fungi/microbial/other vegan based proteins).

3. FEASTS technological knowledge base creation

Cells and cell lines are obtained from several sources - see FEASTS D3.1 for more info. Media and scaffolds can use several ingredients - FEASTS D3.3. Cells will growth and mature on bioreactors that can be of several types - FEASTS D3.4 will provide insights on those. For CM and CSF, it is required specific EU infrastructure, FEASTS D3.5. Deliverables D3.3, D3.4 and D3.5 are due by the end of FEASTS second year.

4. Specifics: Media is an important cost-driver for CM and CSF production, affecting its final cost, environmental performance and, importantly, food resilience and security. Media are composed by substrates sources for the cells, i.e. nutrients, such as amino acids (derived from plant hydrolysates, algae or microbial fermentation), sugars (like glucose from corn or sugarcane), vitamins and minerals (sourced from plants, algae or microbial cells). Other components like growth factors (from microbial fermentation, plants and algae cells) can be used to aid cell growth.

5. Enabling technologies: A special issue on Future Foods journal is set up to make knowledge on state of art of key enabling technologies available on open access ([Link](#))

3.3.2 Recommendations: Cultured Meat and Seafood

A table on the next page summarizes the preliminary recommendations for cultivated meat (CM) and seafood (CSF) sector development in 1 A4 page, which are then elaborated on the next pages for improved readability.

<p>1. Position biotechnology, including Culture Meat (CM) and Cultivated Seafood (CSF) as a critical pillar of the EU food system to ensure resilience and food security by:</p> <p>(a) delivering affordable and safe food products with high nutritional value and sensorial qualities, with the potential of high environmental performance, while supporting EU food security and sovereignty, and achieving the</p> <p>(b) Mission goals and Development steps for CM and CSF as defined on a preliminary Strategic Road Map for the CM/CSF Sector (FEASTS Deliverable 2.3) and to be further developed as a white paper/report (FEASTS Deliverable 2.6, Nov 2026).</p> <p>2. Develop a Stewardship Model Governance Framework and a 10-year EU Strategy for Cultivated Meat (CM) and Cultivated Seafood (CSF); in which:</p> <p>(a) Stewardship Model Governance framework that follows a food system thinking and aims to create value through the supply chain; and</p> <p>(b) Development a 10-year EU CM and CSF Strategy with clear targets for CM, CSF, and cultivate dairy products development and commercialization.</p> <p>3. Research & Innovation investment to support pre-competitive knowledge to develop technologies</p> <p>(a) at low TRL through Public Investment in Foundational R&D;</p> <p>(b) intermediate TRL Specific Research Innovation Thrust R&D programs as well as implementing, and</p> <p>(c) Data Sharing Repositories to foster EU competitiveness on this sector.</p> <p>4. EU Investment infrastructure and Scale-UP in Europe's biomanufacturing capacity, to foster new food products to reach higher TRL and commercialization, including</p> <p>(a) access to open access infrastructure to scale up and analytics for quality assurance, reducing CAPEX burden on intermediate scale up stages;</p> <p>(b) Develop regional biomanufacturing hubs, e.g. with co-financing from EIB; and</p> <p>(c) Support producers of raw materials for cellular agriculture sector, reducing reliance on costly imports.</p>	<p>5. Foster Sector Growth, including</p> <p>(a) Financial Instruments that range from support SME and startup growth, EU Alternative Protein Investment Funds, loan guarantees, blended finance instruments for infrastructure scale-up and de-risks private capital investment, entry market tax incentives and/or green public procurement to CM and CSF;</p> <p>(b) Public-Private partnerships (PPPs), including entry points and investment of incumbent companies on the sector, which provides positive signals to further investment, long-term predictability, exit strategies to investors and innovators, and pathways for commercialization; and</p> <p>(c) (Re)training the Specialize workforce, pooling expertise from academia, startups, and industry food incumbent companies, to foster dedicated skills on STEM education, entrepreneurship, and advanced food system analysis, through training on food biotechnology research and commercialization.</p> <p>6. Industrial Standards, International Harmonization & Trade Readiness. Those include:</p> <p>(a) standards on Minimal criteria for edible cells, approved substances for use in CM/CSF manufacturing, and Substance of concern with thresholds;</p> <p>(b) bilateral recognition agreements and bilateral safety standards to smooth approval of regulatory submissions across the different legal jurisdictions; and</p> <p>(c) Create export/import pathways for cultivated products to encourage EU leadership in global trade worldwide.</p> <p>7. Food safety and consumer information.</p> <p>Actions include:</p> <p>(a) Establish Regulatory Sandboxes for Cultivated Meat and Seafood, much like in the UK, will help companies navigate the novel food regulatory framework and demonstrate their products' safety and compliance;</p> <p>(b) Regulation for approval process to be smart, reasonable and efficient, example including fast-track approval pathways for low-risk products pre-submission consultation services; and pre-approved list of safety ingredients; and</p> <p>(c) Support safety and nutritional studies, as novel food EFSA submissions can be costly (average €1–2M for novel food dossiers); and</p> <p>(d) provide consumers with clear information and access to products, establishing Labelling and certification systems, Living labs, and consumer communication frameworks.</p> <p>8. Valorisation and just transition strategy for food system actors, by</p> <p>(a) developing metrics such as Key Performance Indicators for CM and CSF aligned with TRL.</p> <p>b) Business models with different levels of (de)centralization, and</p> <p>c) Value created for all stakeholders, including mechanisms to support farmer's transition into the CM sector,</p>
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Table 1: Summary of recommendation for development of the CM/CSF sector

1. Position biotechnology, including Culture Meat (CM) and Cultivated Seafood (CSF) as a critical pillar of the EU food system supporting EU food production resilience and food security:

a) Such strategy is vital in reducing EU reliance on imports and mitigating supply chain vulnerabilities through local, biotech-enabled food production (cultured meat, microbial fermentation, precision fermentation, ingredient modification through fermentation) to support long-term food system resilience. Food Biotechnology at broad, and CM and CSF in particular have the potential to **deliver affordable and safe food products with high nutritional value and sensorial qualities**. Considering the unique distinct features of the designed processes of the respective production processes, they have the **potential of high environmental performance**, while **supporting EU food security and sovereignty**.

b) **Mission goals and Development steps for CM and CSF** were defined on a preliminary **Strategic Road Map for the CM/CSF Sector** (FEASTS Deliverable 2.3) and will be further developed as a white paper/report (FEASTS Deliverable 2.6, Nov 2026). Such strategical plan aims to bring EU to a competitive advantage position, unlock innovation, grow EU economy, contribute to EU industrialization, create high value jobs, reduce import dependence (especially seafood), and solidify Europe's role as a global leader in sustainable food, while leading to a fair protein transition.

2. Develop a Stewardship Model Governance framework and a 10-year EU Strategy for Cultivated Meat and Cultivated Seafood:

a) Prioritize values-based approach to development and governance of CM and CSF integrating science-based regulation with public deliberation, ethical reflection, long-term foresight, and multi-stakeholder participation to ensure food biotech contributes to EU food system priorities (climate, nutrition, circularity, community, resilience). Build public trust and legitimacy by guiding innovation based on collective good, foresight, and adaptive governance. **Such model should introduce food system thinking and stewardship model** Interactive tool for visualising the value created through the supply chain

b) Development a **10-year EU Cultivated Meat and Cultivated Seafood Strategy**, supported by the stewardship model and learnings taken from similar EU experiences (such as the EU's Hydrogen Strategy) such plan should include clear targets for cultivated meat, cultivated seafood, and cultivate dairy products development and commercialization.

3. Research & Innovation investment. Innovation needs investment, there is a need to support pre-competitive knowledge to develop technologies at low and intermediate TRL (e.g. through Horizon 2026 calls and Research Innovation thrust areas) as well as data sharing repositories that can foster EU competitiveness on this sector creating:

a) Public Investment in Foundational R&D, may include Fund Horizon Europe projects in under-researched areas such as (i) cell line development (e.g. for salmon, turkey, tuna, duck, and local bovine and porcine herds in the EU); (ii) Serum-free food-grade media based and low-cost growth factor production; (iii) Novel bioreactors (e.g. made of thermostable bioplastics, steel alternatives) able to reduce capex costs, while improving environmental performance, for large-scale mammalian cell proliferation as well as structured products; (iv) Downstream processes for cell edible biomass harvest; (v) Novel culture meat scaffolds and 3D food formulation; (vi) Food formulation, packaging, storage and preservation methods; (vii) introduction of transversal technologies such as machine Learning, artificial intelligence applications in cultured proteins and automation of large-scale manufacturing of animal cells for food applications.

b) Specific Research Innovation thrust research programs, to reach intermediate TRLs, which can be species or theme specific, such as focused on fish & seafood (Low-cost serum-free media, cold-adapted cell line banks); mammalian and avian cultivated meat (cell lines, culture media, etc); and dairy products (Mammary cell line development and precision fermentation hybrid models); as well as transversal ones to cultivated meat and seafood, such as specific bioreactors, food-safe scaffolds, and or 3D structured tissue engineering processes.

c) Repositories of Key Enabling Technologies and Safety Data, with different layers of use, ranging from open-source to trade tools developed assets. Public R&D reduces duplication and creates open innovation platforms. Fish and seafood research, as well as bovine milk is particularly underdeveloped compared to meat species. For example, to establish EU cell line and scaffold repositories as public resources will be useful for the all industry. Currently, there are no dedicated cell repositories of animal species used as food in the EU, which delays scientific research and innovation.

4. EU Investment infrastructure and Scale-UP in Europe's biomanufacturing capacity. Those measures are crucial for new food products to reach higher TRL and commercialization, including access test-beds infrastructure.

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a) **Open access infrastructure to scale up and analytics for quality assurance**, including the creation of Create open-access pilot facilities (bioreactors, media production) for startups in cultivated meat and seafood, allowing to assess novel technologies (cells, media, etc) in shared infrastructure producing cell biomass and cultivated meat products on quantities enough for regulatory requirements and market testing, while reducing g CAPEX burden and speeding commercialization.

b) **Support regional biomanufacturing hubs**, with shared access to large bioreactors and food structuring manufacture, e.g. with co-financing from EIB, as Europe currently lacks scaled manufacturing capacity for cultivated proteins.

c) **Support producers of raw materials for cellular agriculture sector**, such as cell food-grade substrate ingredients and food-safe growth factor for media production within Europe, reducing reliance on costly imports.

5. Financial Instruments for Sector Growth, Public-Private partnerships (PPPs) and train the Specialize workforce, pooling expertise from academia, startups, and industry food incumbent companies.

a) **Financial Instruments for Sector Growth**, such instruments can include: (i) Measures to support **SME and startup growth** drive EU innovation, resilience and competitiveness; (ii) Launch an **EU Alternative Protein Investment Fund under the EIB** to co-finance cultivated protein projects; (iii) Provide loan guarantees and blended **finance instruments for infrastructure scale-up**, as blended finance de-risks private capital investment; (iv) Fiscal instruments such as **entry market** tax returns related with regulatory burden, environmental benefits, or increase on domestic production; and or (v) use **green procurement programs** for public institutions to include cultivated proteins.

b) **Create incentives for Public-Private partnerships to develop the sector** Provide incentives to secure investment of incumbent companies on the sector on cooperation with academics and start-ups, provides positive signals to further investment, gives long-term predictability and exit strategies to investors and innovators, and robust pathways for commercialization.

c) **(Re)Training the workforce for Cellular agriculture**. Provide education to build future food systems: Address need for STEM education, teaching entrepreneurial skills and advanced food system analysis, provide capacity building and training programmes to support food biotechnology research and expansion.

6. Industrial Standards, International Harmonization & Trade Readiness.

Those include:

a) specific international standards such as the ones that define: (i) **Minimal criteria for edible cells**, (ii) **approved substances for use in CM/CSF manufacturing** (media, scaffolds, etc), (iii) **Substance of concern with thresholds** that can remain on final product defined, and (iv) sustainability metrics defined.

b) **Pursue bilateral recognition agreements** with early-approval countries outside the EU (e.g.,UK, Switzerland, Singapore, USA, Australia) and develop bilateral safety standards that allow smooth approval of regulatory submissions across the different legal jurisdictions.

c) **Create export/import pathways** for cultivated products, tackling both the global north and the global south, to encourage EU leadership in global trade while addressing the food equity and access worldwide.

7. Food safety and consumer information. Develop robust criteria and guidelines with participation of academia, industry, primary producers, civil society, and consumer organisations in defining criteria to support health and nutrition goals and increase legitimacy and public trust in safety of food produced through biotechnology. Namely:

a) **Establish Regulatory Sandboxes for Cultivated Meat and Seafood:** Regulatory sandboxes, much like in the UK, will help companies navigate the novel food regulatory framework and demonstrate their products' safety and compliance, while also enhancing the EFSA's scientific knowledge of the field. This type of framework could include pre-submission consultations to companies, which could potentially streamline the approval timeline while upholding high safety standards. Companies interested in participating in the sandbox could apply, and those not selected will still have access to the program's outputs, ensuring the initiative benefits the broader industry.

b) **Regulation to be smart, reasonable and efficient:** Potential actions include the streamline EFSA Approval Processes, such as introducing fast-track approval pathways for low-risk, cell-based products (e.g., cultivated milk proteins with GRAS-like status, cell lines as ingredients with full safety assessments); provide pre-submission consultation services; and importantly pre-approved list of safety ingredients (media ingredients, growth factors, scaffolds).

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c) **Support safety and nutritional studies:** Study solutions to avoid that safety compliance become business entry barriers, note that novel food EFSA submissions can be costly (average €1–2M for novel food dossiers).

d) **Consumers need clear information and access to products, potential actions include:** (i) **Labelling and certification systems** for CM/CSF that address issues as animal cruelty free, environment performance, nutritional value, etc, (ii) **Living labs** where consumers can try the novel products of CM/CSF; and (iii) **Consumer Communication Framework**, that funds public awareness and transparency campaigns on safety, sustainability; and nutritional features to counter misinformation.

8. Valorisation and just transition strategy for food system actors: Adopt systems thinking to integrate sustainability principles, techno-economic considerations and societal aspects. **Valorisation need metrics and business models**, thus it is recommended that:

a) **Key Performance Indicators for Cultivated Meat and Cultivated Seafood process and product development**, with quantified metrics aligned with TRL for the different critical supporting technologies.

b) **Business models with different levels of (de)centralization**, ensure equity and security are studied and implemented

c) **Value created for all stakeholders:** Mechanisms to support **farmer's transition into the CM sector**, including ingredient sourcing for CM and CSF or direct involvement on production of CM and CSF to obtain high value revenue streams. This anticipates disruption to traditional farming and fisheries and provides grounds to support inclusive transitions ensuring rural livelihoods, fair opportunities, and balanced regional development.

Those recommendations will be refined and discussed over the last months of FEASTS activities. A table on the next page summarizes such recommendations on 1 A4 page

3.3.3 Comments: Cultured Meat and Seafood

- **Cultured Meat and Culture Seafood:** Cultivated Meat and Cultivated Seafood products derived from animal cell can play a pivotal role in achieving the EU Green Deal, Farm to Fork Strategy, and 2050 climate neutrality goals by providing low-carbon, safe, and resilient protein alternatives. Animal Cells from terrestrial, avian and aquatic animals' species can be used as food sources and provide a

nutritional and organoleptic profile akin to conventional meat and seafood, whilst using a fraction of the resources of its counterpart. In addition, cell-lines can be used as ingredients of hybrid products containing other alternative proteins and enhance their taste and texture.

- **Terrestrial and avian cultured meat:** Beyond its sustainability and nutritional potential, cultured meat production could strengthen the EU's food security and resilience by enabling meat production without reliance on antibiotics, something several companies are already achieving. In this manner, cultured meat can also safeguard the current EU food chains from potential zoonotic outbreaks and antibiotic-resistant microorganisms targeting livestock (such as MRSA ST398). Despite the EU's successful efforts to reduce antibiotic use in food-producing animals, the majority of antibiotics in the EU are still administered to livestock, continuing to contribute to antimicrobial resistance. Furthermore, there are pioneering start-ups in the EU invested in models that integrate farmers and align with the existing European protein landscape. Research suggests that cultured meat could reduce GHG emissions by up to 92%, land use by 90%, and water use by 78% compared to conventional livestock, and the global cultured meat and seafood market is projected to exceed €20 billion by 2035, with early adopters gaining the largest competitive advantage. Among the five continents, Europe has the highest concentration of SMEs in the cultured meat and seafood sector, with over 54 companies actively conducting research and attempting to scale manufacturing. Despite this strong research presence, Europe trails behind other regions in terms of regulatory submissions and has yet to bring any products to market, falling behind countries like Singapore, Australia, and the United States.
- **Cultured Seafood:** While being a sizable consumer and producer of fish and other marine organisms, the EU still imports upwards of 70% of its seafood. Using cell lines from seafood as a source of protein can ensure local, traceable, heavy metal-free supply, as well as aiding the recovery of essential fisheries and balanced ecosystems. Furthermore, cell lines as a food source of seafood can be a sustainable alternative to offshore aquaculture by reducing the eutrophication levels at sea. Seafood cell lines are not prone to accumulate mercury, cadmium, and persistent organic pollutants like polychlorinated biphenyls– all commonly found in seafood from traditional fisheries. The global cultured meat and seafood market is projected to exceed €20 billion by 2035, with early adopters gaining the largest competitive advantage. Among the five continents, Europe has the highest concentration of SMEs in the cultured meat

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and seafood sector, with over 54 companies actively conducting research and attempting to scale manufacturing. However, most are focusing on terrestrial species, with only 5 companies in the continent publicly stating their focus on seafood. Despite this strong research presence, Europe trails behind other regions in terms of regulatory submissions and has yet to bring any products to market, falling behind countries like Singapore, Australia, and the United States.

4. Final remarks

FEASTS ambition is for the project findings to serve as support tool for informed policy and decision-making in the EU. To fulfil such a mission, FEASTS, was designed as a think-tank, developing stewardships models, stabilising the state of art for the sector, gathering evidence base information, adopting a Food Systems Thinking approach and multidimensional impact assessments.

FEASTS is the only Horizon based project dedicated to cultivated meat and seafood. While progressing steadily on its objectives, FEASTS is a short programme of 3 years, and the sector development will carry on over such period, generating better technology, additional market deployment of products, and needing accompanying measures to support and monitor such development.

Cellular agriculture and Cultivated Meat and Seafood in particular have very distinct features, concerning the nutritional potential of the final product, its potential environmental performance and ability to improve food security. Therefore, as the end of the second-year approaches (Nov 2026). it would be crucial to create another EU call that can follow up on FEASTS results and ensure EU competitiveness on this sector has an opportunity.